

22NRM02 STANBC

D6: Wavelength dependent MAC

Report on the determination of wavelength-dependent MAC values and wavelength dependent filter-based light absorption photometer calibration factors including multiple scattering factors, with their associated measurement uncertainties (target uncertainties < 15 % for 95 % confidence level) based on the calibration in D5

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable:

TROPOS

Due date of the deliverable:

31.05.2025

Actual submission date of the deliverable:

02.06.2026

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open

Deliverable D6

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The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

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Glossary

AAE	Ångström absorption exponent
b_{abs}	Light absorption coefficient
BC	Black carbon
$D_{N,\text{mob}}$	Number mean diameter (mobility-diameter based)
$D_{V,\text{mob}}$	Volume mean diameter (mobility-diameter based)
eBC	Equivalent Black Carbon
EC	Elemental carbon
EMS	Extinction minus scattering
λ	Wavelength of light
MAC	Mass absorption coefficient
OCU	Organic coating unit
OFR	Oxidation flow reactor
PAS	Photoacoustic spectroscopy
PAX	Photoacoustic extincniometer
PTAAM	Photo-thermal aerosol absorption monitor
PTI	Photo-thermal interferometry
SMPS	Scanning Mobility Particle Size Spectrometer
SSA	Single scattering albedo

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1. Summary

This study presents wavelength-dependent mass absorption cross sections (MAC) and calibration factors for filter-based photometers derived from controlled laboratory experiments with well-characterized aerosols. Using soot particles with varying coating thickness, MAC is evaluated as a function of single scattering albedo (SSA). Compared to common core-shell model predictions, MAC can grow less or even decrease with increasing coating, suggesting that morphological changes, such as restructuring and non-ideal mixing states, can suppress the expected lensing effect. Comparisons with optical models indicate better agreement with fractal and porous particle representations than with idealized core-shell structures. These findings emphasize the importance of particle morphology and growth pathways for interpreting aerosol absorption and improving photometer calibration.

The wavelength dependence of the MAC agrees better with expectations, since the higher imaginary part of the refractive index in the UV, compared to the red or near-infrared wavelengths of organic matter, leads to stronger UV absorption, independent of morphological effects.

2. Introduction

Black-carbon-containing particles are among the most efficient atmospheric light absorbers, influencing the Earth's radiative balance both directly (Haywood and Shine, 1995) and through interactions with clouds and atmospheric dynamics (Koch & Del Genio, 2010). In addition to their climatic relevance, these particles pose risks to human health due to toxic compounds associated with their surfaces. Consequently, regulatory frameworks such as the European Union Air Quality Directive 2024 (European Parliament, 2024) now require monitoring of black carbon concentrations.

Filter-based light absorption photometers are widely deployed in air quality and atmospheric monitoring networks because of their robustness and operational simplicity. These instruments determine aerosol light absorption from the attenuation of light transmitted through particle-loaded filters. The measured attenuation is converted into an absorption coefficient using a multiple-scattering correction factor (C), and subsequently into equivalent black carbon (eBC) mass concentration via the mass absorption cross-section (MAC). However, both C and MAC are inherently wavelength-dependent and strongly influenced by aerosol properties such as particle size distribution (Renzi et al., 2026), mixing state, and chemical composition. The use of fixed, manufacturer-defined values therefore introduces systematic biases in derived absorption coefficients and eBC concentrations.

Furthermore, filter-based measurements are affected by artefacts including filter matrix scattering effects and loading-dependent sensitivity changes (Drinovec et al. 2015, and references therein), which require additional corrections. These challenges highlight the need for traceable calibration procedures and a rigorous quantification of associated uncertainties.

This deliverable addresses these limitations by determining wavelength-dependent MAC values and calibration factors for filter-based photometers, including multiple-scattering correction factors, across a wide range of aerosol optical conditions. The work builds on controlled laboratory calibrations using well-characterised test aerosols covering a large single scattering albedo (SSA) range, and is anchored to reference in situ absorption measurement techniques such as photothermal interferometry (PTI, Drinovec et al., 2022) and extinction-minus-scattering (EMS).

A key objective is the establishment of calibration functions and correction factors with well-defined uncertainty budgets, targeting expanded uncertainties below 15 % at a 95 % confidence level. This includes the assessment of method-specific uncertainties, particularly for indirect techniques such as EMS at high SSA, and the evaluation of wavelength-dependent responses of different photometer types.

Overall, this report provides a framework for improving the accuracy, comparability, and traceability of filter-based aerosol light absorption measurements, supporting both regulatory monitoring and climate-relevant atmospheric research.

This deliverable builds upon methodologies, datasets, and calibration results developed in preceding project deliverables. Cross-references to the relevant deliverables are provided throughout the document.

3. Instrumentation and Experimental Setup

3.1. Reference instruments

Light absorption reference instruments include a three-wavelength Extinction Minus Scattering setup (EMS) and a two-wavelength Photo-Thermal Interferometry instrument (PTAAM, Drinovec et al. 2022) and a PAX (Droplet Measurement Technologies). The traceability of the calibration of these instruments was reported in Deliverable D2.

3.2. Filter absorption Photometers

The devices under test (DUT) comprised a range of commercially available high-end and mid-cost filter-based photometers, including Aethalometers (models AE22, AE31, AE33, AE36s; Aerosol Magee Scientific, Slovenia), microAeth instruments (models MA200 and MA350; AethLabs, USA), the BC 1054 multi-wavelength black carbon analyser (Met One Instruments, France), and the multi-angle absorption photometer (MAAP 5012, Thermo Scientific, USA).

3.3. Supporting instruments

Aerosol mobility size distributions were measured using an SMPS to derive geometric mean diameter of the particle number and volume size distributions. The volume size distribution was calculated assuming that the volume equivalent diameter equals the mobility diameter (i.e. assuming spherical particles). Carbonaceous composition (OC/EC) was determined by thermal–optical analysis using the EUSAAR2 protocol with minor modifications, accounting for gas-phase adsorption via a dual-filter setup.

3.4. Aerosol generation and experimental setup

A detailed overview of the experimental setup is provided in Deliverable 5 and the accompanying manuscript (Hammer et al. 2026). Therefore, only a brief overview is presented here.

Fresh soot particles were generated using a miniCAST 5201 (Jing Ltd., Switzerland) combustion generator and, where required, coated with secondary organic matter from α -pinene ozonolysis. For uncoated soot experiments, the coating unit was bypassed. The generated aerosols were diluted, conditioned, and distributed to the measurement instruments via a multi-port flow system ensuring representative sampling across varying flow rates.

In addition, ammonium sulphate particles were produced using a nebuliser system, dried, and size-conditioned. These were either measured directly or mixed with soot particles to create internally and externally mixed aerosol populations under controlled humidity conditions.

Ambient-like aerosols, consisting of mixtures of soot, inorganic salts, and mineral dust, were generated using the PALMA setup (Horender, 2021), where particles were homogenised in a turbulent flow reactor prior to sampling.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of aerosol generation and sampling. Figure taken from Hammer et al. (2026).

4. Experimental Design

The experimental design was developed to address several questions.

- a. Comparison of reference instruments for the particle light absorption coefficient (Deliverables 2 & 5)
- b. Calibration of single- and multi- wavelength filter-based light absorption photometers (Deliverable 5)
- c. Comparison of methods for determining the elemental carbon (EC) concentration
- d. Derivation of wavelength dependent MAC values by combining the results obtained in a) to c)

Due to flow limitations, the instruments were divided into three groups, and the same aerosol type was measured sequentially in each group. Groups 1 and 2 were used for basic aerosol characterization and instruments under test (DUT), and Group 3 was used to derive the MAC values. To ensure comparability between the groups, one reference instrument, the PTAAM-2 λ , as well as the PAX were operated in all groups.

The instruments were operated with their native time resolution to achieve the optimal signal-to-noise ratio. The run time in Groups 1&2 varied between 30 and 60 minutes, depending on the aerosol concentration, whereas the run time in Group 3 was about two hours to allow for sufficient filter loading for subsequent offline analysis. Table 1 gives an overview of the test aerosols and performed experiments. Details can be found in D5.

Table 1: Summary of test aerosols and experiments.

Aerosol Series	Composition	Instrument groups	Purpose
A1	Fresh soot, size 1	Group 1	Photometer calibration
		Group 2	Photometer calibration
		Group 3	Derivation of MAC
	Soot size 1 with thin coating	Group 1	Photometer calibration
		Group 2	Photometer calibration
		Group 3	Derivation of MAC
	Soot size 1 with thick coating	Group 1	Photometer calibration
		Group 2	Photometer calibration
		Group 3	Derivation of MAC
A2	Fresh soot, size 2	Group 1	Photometer calibration
		Group 2	Photometer calibration
		Group 3	Derivation of MAC
	Soot size 2 with thin coating	Group 1	Photometer calibration
		Group 2	Photometer calibration
		Group 3	Derivation of MAC
	Soot size 2 with thick coating	Group 1	Photometer calibration
		Group 2	Photometer calibration
		Group 3	Derivation of MAC
A3	Mixture of soot and salt	Group 1	Photometer calibration
		Group 2	Photometer calibration
		Group 3	Derivation of MAC
A5	Ambient like particles	Group 1	Photometer calibration
		Group 2	Photometer calibration
		Group 3	Derivation of MAC

5. Data Processing

5.1. Derived optical parameters

Absorption Ångström exponent

The spectral slope of aerosol light absorption coefficients is given by the Absorption Ångström exponent (AAE) defined by

$$AAE = \frac{-\ln\left(\frac{b_{abs}(\lambda_1)}{b_{abs}(\lambda_2)}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2}\right)}$$

For each multiwavelength instrument, the spectral slope was calculated to convert the absorption coefficient measured at one wavelength to another wavelength, often used when comparing instruments at different wavelengths. Conversion of the light absorption coefficient for a single wavelength instrument to another wavelength was performed using the AAE derived from PTAAM-2λ.

Single Scattering Albedo

The single scattering albedo (SSA) describes the contribution of light scattering to total light extinction. It is defined as the ratio of light scattering to extinction coefficient (scattering plus absorption) by

$$SSA = \frac{b_{sca}}{b_{sca} + b_{abs}}$$

5.2. EC concentrations

Elemental Carbon (EC) was derived from the thermo-optical EUSAAR-2 protocol (Cavalli et al. 2010). The loading density was converted to an EC concentration using aerosol flow and loaded spot area. The standard uncertainty of this device is reported along with the OC and EC concentrations.

5.3. Determination of MAC

MAC values were derived from absorption measured by PTAAM-2λ and EC concentration from the thermo-optical analyzer by

$$MAC = \frac{b_{abs}}{m_{EC}}$$

Table 2: Calculated MAC and uncertainties ($k=2$). Absorption coefficients from PTAAM-2 λ and EC mass concentrations from the thermo-optical analyzer.

Experiment series	MAC [m ² /g]		b _{abs} [1/Mm]				m _{EC} [μg/m ³]	
	450 nm	808 nm	450 nm	808 nm	450 nm	808 nm	450 nm	808 nm
A1 size 1 bare soot	5.28 ± 0.81	2.61 ± 0.46	26.5 ± 2.2	13.1 ± 1.6	5.02 ± 0.64			
A1 thin coating	4.57 ± 0.82	1.96 ± 0.40	28.7 ± 2.4	12.3 ± 1.5	6.28 ± 1.00			
A1 thick coating	4.27 ± 0.64	1.64 ± 0.29	32.8 ± 2.8	12.6 ± 1.6	7.68 ± 0.96			
A2 size 2 bare soot	6.84 ± 1.06	3.41 ± 0.61	49.4 ± 4.1	24.6 ± 3.1	7.22 ± 0.94			
A2 thin coating	8.94 ± 1.31	3.63 ± 0.63	69.9 ± 5.9	28.4 ± 3.5	7.82 ± 0.94			
A2 thick coating	8.10 ± 1.23	3.33 ± 0.59	58.8 ± 4.9	24.2 ± 3.0	7.26 ± 0.92			
A3 soot-salt mixture	4.06 ± 0.75	1.93 ± 0.40	20.6 ± 1.7	9.8 ± 1.2	5.08 ± 0.84			
A5 ambient like	8.48 ± 1.36	3.47 ± 0.64	95.7 ± 8.0	39.1 ± 4.8	11.28 ± 1.54			

6. Results

6.1. Comparison of reference absorption instruments

Comparison of light absorption coefficients derived from PTAAM-2 λ and EMS revealed that EMS gave higher values by a factor of 1.47 and 1.16 for wavelength 450 and 808, respectively. The coefficients of determination, R^2 , were 0.97 and 0.90 for 450 and 808 nm, respectively. The higher uncertainty at 808 nm is mainly caused by the lower absorption coefficients at 808 nm compared with 450 nm, resulting in a lower signal-to-noise ratio. Larger deviations were observed for low absorption coefficients, where EMS is known to be more uncertain than PTAAM-2 λ . Furthermore, the extrapolation of EMS measurements from 635 nm to 808 nm using the Ångström absorption exponent may introduce an additional bias.

Table 3: Absorption coefficients from EMS and PTAAM-2 λ based on the linear relationship

$$b_{\text{abs, EMS}} = m \cdot b_{\text{abs, PTAAM}}$$

Wavelength [nm]	Slope (m)	Expanded uncertainty of slope ($k=2$)
450	1.47	±0.07
808*	1.16	±0.28

*EMS converted to 808 using AAE from PTAAM-2 λ

6.2. Mass absorption cross sections (MAC)

Results of the mass absorption cross section (MAC) obtained from the laboratory experiments are shown in Fig. 2 as a function of the single scattering albedo (SSA). SSA is used here as a proxy for coating, as scattering generally increases with increasing coating material. Therefore, MAC values are presented as a function of the corresponding SSA.

Results for wavelengths of 450 nm and 808 nm are shown in blue and red, respectively. For both series A1 and A2, the points for uncoated and coated particles are connected by solid and dashed lines. Experiments A5 and A3 are shown as individual data points.

Figure 2: MAC values versus the SSA for experiments A1, A2, A3 and A5. The color indicates the wavelength, i.e. the blue lines and labels show MAC values for 450 nm and the red lines and symbols show MAC values for 808 nm.

6.3. Comparison with scattering models

6.3.1. Model descriptions

Coated sphere

Simulation of the coating experiments was performed using a spherical black carbon (BC) core surrounded by a concentric spherical shell, with the core positioned at the center. The core diameter was kept constant at 75 nm, while the shell thickness was increased stepwise until the total particle diameter reached 238 nm.

The BC core was assigned a complex refractive index of $1.85 - 0.79i$, whereas the coating was assumed to be non-absorbing, with a refractive index of $1.5 + 0.0i$. Using the scattering code pyMieScatt (Sumlin et al., 2018), the single scattering albedo and absorption cross section were calculated at a wavelength of 808 nm. The mass absorption cross section (MAC) was then derived assuming a bulk core density of 2 g/cm^3 .

Fractal core with porous coating

The BC core was assumed to have a fractal structure with a fractal dimension of $D_f=2.0$, consisting of 15 primary particles with radii of 15 nm. The total mass of this fractal core was set equal to that of the BC core used in the coated-sphere model.

The coating was simulated by incrementally adding spherical coating particles (monomers) with radii of 15 nm. These were preferentially placed in the void spaces near the center of the aggregate, progressively filling internal gaps and making the overall particle morphology increasingly compact and spherical. In total, 500 coating monomers were added, resulting in an outer particle that was nearly spherical.

A positional constraint was applied to both core and coating particles, restricting their locations to a hexagonal packing lattice. This approach enabled the construction of aggregates with a wide range of fractal dimensions while ensuring a well-defined void fraction of approximately 26% across the volume of the particle.

The scattering calculations were performed using the MSTM model (Mackowski, 2012). Optical properties were first computed for the bare BC core and subsequently recalculated as the coating steadily increased.

Notes on the model:

- The model simulates particle growth of a fractal aggregate by successively filling voids similar to a cluster–particle aggregation process. However, it should be noted that this is not a physical aggregation mechanism; instead, particle positions are assigned through random selection of positions with boundary conditions.
- The porous structure of the coating shell is characterized by characteristic sizes much smaller than the wavelength of light ($d_{\text{monomere}} \ll \lambda$). As a result, internal scattering within the shell is largely suppressed. A more rigorous investigation of the validity of this assumption would require additional simulations using models MSTM and ADDA (Jurkin and Hoekstra, 2011) combined with effective medium theory (EMT) as shown in e.g. Zhuromskyy (2016).

Figure 3: The images depict the structural composition of a particle derived from the fractal-porosity model. From left to right: The first sample is a bare BC particle with 15 monomers; the second sample is a slightly coated particle with a total of 60 monomers; the third sample is a strongly coated particle with 500 monomers.

6.3.2. Model results

The porosity model and a core-shell model were run to simulate coated fractal BC particles. All simulations were performed at a wavelength of 808 nm (PTAAM-2 λ wavelength). Results are summarized in Table 4. Dimensions are given as the volume equivalent diameter core (d_{core}) and the outer diameter of the entire particle (d_{outer}). For both models, the refractive indices were set to $m_{core}=1.85-0.79j$ and $m_{shell}= 1.5-0.0j$. The bulk density of the core was assumed to be 2.0 g/cm³.

Figure 4 shows how the modeled MAC develops when coating the fractal soot core in comparison to the measurements. The porosity model agrees much better with the measured values than a MIE core-shell model. The porosity model considers a fractal core, which leads to lower absorption compared to the core-shell model, where the BC is centered within the particle, resulting in a stronger lensing and therefore enhancement effect.

In the porosity model, the simulation still assumes a spherical outer shell, which can also contribute to lensing. Non-spherical outer shells were not simulated, but it is likely that they would also affect the absorption enhancement.

Table 4: Summary of scattering calculations.

Particle dimensions		Coated sphere		Fractal core with porous coating		
d_{core} [nm]	d_{outer} [nm]	MAC [m ² /g]	SSA	Number of spherules	MAC [m ² /g]	SSA
75	75	3.51	0.02	15	3.81	0.02
75	88	3.96	0.03	25	3.89	0.03
75	107	4.41	0.06	45	3.91	0.06
75	127	4.79	0.11	75	4.03	0.12
75	139	5.00	0.15	100	4.16	0.18
75	152	5.23	0.22	130	4.13	0.25
75	169	5.54	0.32	180	4.49	0.36
75	189	5.93	0.45	250	4.69	0.50
75	211	6.39	0.58	350	4.94	0.63
75	238	6.97	0.71	500	5.23	0.75

Figure 4: Intercomparison of MAC values measured at 808 nm and modelled MAC values. The green dashed line shows the result of the fractal-porosity model. The labels indicate volume equivalent diameter. The black dash dotted line shows the result from the corresponding core-shell model.

6.4. Filter-based photometer calibration

Filter-based absorption photometers often make use of a factory-set mass absorption cross section (MAC) and a multiple scattering factor. Calculation schemes differ among instrument types. In Deliverable 5, the measurements were presented and the light attenuation coefficient b_{atn} was recalculated using an equation common to all filter-based instruments. This general equation is

$$b_{atn} = C \cdot b_{abs} ,$$

meaning that the measured light attenuation is coupled to the true light absorption coefficient via a filter scattering factor C (Loading effects were already corrected for). The C factor is caused by multiple scattering within the filter matrix and is an instrument/filter property. However, its value can also be affected by other aerosol properties, for example how particles are deposited within the filter matrix. The MAC is not part of C factors but an aerosol property; however, correlations between C and MAC may exist. MAC values are to be used for deriving follow-up products, such as equivalent black carbon (eBC) from absorption coefficients. Therefore, MAC should be chosen by the scientist depending on the application, and not treated as an instrument-specific constant. The primary effort should focus on calibrating filter-based photometers for light absorption in order to determine reliable C values.

It should be noted that loading compensation must still be applied by the user or by the instrument’s internal correction mechanism. The C values discussed here are only valid for low filter loadings or loading compensated data.

The uncertainties given by PTAAM-2λ are considered fully systematic with u_{PTAAM} being 8.4 and 12.4% for wavelength 450 and 808 nm with a confidence level of 95% (k=2) and do not average out when combining results from multiple experiments. The same applies to the devices under test (DUT), for which uncertainties are considered systematic and amount 4% (confidence level 95%, k = 2) as reported in D5. For each DUT and experiment the uncertainty (conf. level 95%, k=2) is given by

$$u_{C,DUT} = \sqrt{u_{DUT}^2 + u_{PTAAM}^2}$$

and amounts 9.7% and 13% for 405 nm and 808 nm, respectively.

Table 5: Instrument-specific C-values and associated uncertainties with confidence level k=2 for each experiment and wavelength.

				C-values at 808 nm						
Group	number median diameter, $D_{N,mob}$	volume median diameter, $D_{V,mob}$	SSA	AE33	AE36s	AE22	MA200	MA350	BC-1054	AE31
A1 size 1 bare soot	76.4	162	0.02	6.16+/-0.6	5.91+/-0.57	6.18+/-0.6	3.85+/-0.37	4.13+/-0.4	9.03+/-0.88	4.73+/-0.46
A1 thin coating	91.4	145.9	0.2	7.09+/-0.69	6.88+/-0.67	7.32+/-0.71	4.99+/-0.48	5.04+/-0.49	8.48+/-0.82	
A1 thick coating	117.6	168.5	0.46	6.55+/-0.64	6.26+/-0.61	6.81+/-0.66	3.58+/-0.35	3.71+/-0.36	7.46+/-0.72	
A2 size 2 bare soot	108.6	173.4	0.07	6.51+/-0.63	5.89+/-0.57	5.8+/-0.56	5.46+/-0.53	6.62+/-0.64	9.84+/-0.95	
A2 thin coating	135.8	194.6	0.28	5.52+/-0.54	5.45+/-0.53	5.5+/-0.53	4.11+/-0.4	3.93+/-0.38	7.52+/-0.73	
A2 thick coating	151.2	209.1	0.39	5.55+/-0.54	5.57+/-0.54	5.37+/-0.52	5.15+/-0.5	4.36+/-0.42	6.45+/-0.63	
A3 soot-salt mixture	85.1	346	0.91	5.75+/-0.56	5.5+/-0.53	4.49+/-0.44	4.12+/-0.4	3.85+/-0.37	5.98+/-0.58	
A5 ambient like	140.4	257.3	0.27	4.84+/-0.47	4.66+/-0.45	4.3+/-0.42	3.69+/-0.36	3.74+/-0.36	5.9+/-0.57	
				C values at 405 nm						
Group	number median diameter, $D_{N,mob}$	volume median diameter, $D_{V,mob}$	SSA	AE33	AE36s	AE22	MA200	MA350	BC-1054	AE31
A1 size 1 bare soot	5.57	6.28	3.64	5.75+/-0.75	5.57+/-0.72	6.28+/-0.82	3.64+/-0.47	3.88+/-0.5	7.87+/-1.02	6.95+/-0.9
A1 thin coating	7.69	9.13	5.65	6.68+/-0.87	7.69+/-1	9.13+/-1.19	5.65+/-0.73	5.67+/-0.74	9.57+/-1.24	
A1 thick coating	6.22	6.69	4.54	6.2+/-0.81	6.22+/-0.81	6.69+/-0.87	4.54+/-0.59	4.73+/-0.61	7.8+/-1.01	
A2 size 2 bare soot	5.43	6.20	4.83	5.86+/-0.76	5.43+/-0.71	6.2+/-0.81	4.83+/-0.63	5.98+/-0.78	7.86+/-1.02	
A2 thin coating	5.64	6.16	4.05	5.63+/-0.73	5.64+/-0.73	6.16+/-0.8	4.05+/-0.53	3.9+/-0.51	7.6+/-0.99	3.03+/-0.39
A2 thick coating	6.00	6.94	5.90	5.97+/-0.78	6+/-0.78	6.94+/-0.9	5.9+/-0.77	5.02+/-0.65	6.8+/-0.88	
A3 soot-salt mixture	5.53	5.79	4.70	5.64+/-0.73	5.53+/-0.72	5.79+/-0.75	4.7+/-0.61	4.81+/-0.63	6.8+/-0.88	
A5 ambient like	4.87	4.23	4.06	5+/-0.65	4.87+/-0.63	4.23+/-0.55	4.06+/-0.53	3.96+/-0.51	5.96+/-0.77	

Figure 5: C-values as a function of the volume mean diameter. For each instrument, data at 450 and 808 nm are shown as dots, together with a fitted power-law curve.

In summary, a statistical summary of C-values grouped by instrument and wavelength is shown in Figure 6 and the corresponding values are given in Table 6. The values clearly show that a wavelength dependence is statistically insignificant. C does not depend on wavelength. The range of values for a single instrument to a large part is explained by the size dependence (cf. Figure 5). Within the size range covered in the present study, the average values for Aethalometers of types AE33, AE36s, and AE22 are very similar. For AE31 not enough data are available for a robust analysis. The micro aethalometers MA200 and MA350 using PTFE filter show consistently a lower C value, and the BC-1054 shows a significantly higher C-value.

Figure 6: Statistics of instrument-specific C-values. Shown are the experimental results (points), mean C-values, quartiles (box) and mean \pm 2 SD (whiskers). Values for 450 nm are shown in blue and for 808 nm in red.

Table 6: Statistics of instrument-specific C-values.

Instrument	Wavelength [nm]	n	Mean	uncertainty (k=2)	
				abs.	rel.
AE33	450	8	5.84	0.98	17%
AE33	808	8	5.99	1.44	24%
AE36s	450	8	5.87	1.68	29%
AE36s	808	8	5.77	1.3	23%
AE22	450	8	6.43	2.72	42%
AE22	808	8	5.72	2.08	36%
MA200	450	8	4.67	1.58	34%
MA200	808	8	4.37	1.44	33%
MA350	450	8	4.74	1.62	34%
MA350	808	8	4.42	1.98	45%
BC-1054	450	8	7.53	2.14	28%
BC-1054	808	8	7.58	2.9	38%
AE31	450	2	4.99	5.54	111%
AE31	808	1	4.73		

7. Discussion

7.1. MAC and coating effect

Figure 2 shows the MAC values as function of SSA. SSA here is a robust proxy for the coating, since the scattering increases the more coating material is available. The results of measurements and modeling indicate that the core size influences MAC values. This is well known for spherical cores and also documented for fractal BC core (Romshoo et al. 2021). In particular, the larger core sizes in experiment A2 exhibit higher MAC values compared to A1. With increasing coating, the MAC value decreases, which contrasts with the commonly predicted monotonic increase due to lensing (e.g. Schnaiter et al. 2005, Romshoo et al. 2021). A thin coating, not having much influence on absorption by the lensing effect, can lead to a collapsing of fractal particles, what was observed as the particle number size distribution narrows. This collapsing would increase the cores fractal dimension what is leading to a lower absorption cross section (Romshoo et al. 2021). The decrease of MAC at 808 nm with increasing coating seen in Figure 2 is quite large and continues for even larger coating. At 450 nm, the absorption increases with increasing coating due to the higher coating imaginary part of refractive index compared to 808 nm. This also can be seen by the change of the AAE compared to SSA. However, the MAC values for the data series A1 are still slightly decreasing while increasing for A2. MAC values are subject to uncertainties in the light absorption measurements and the EC mass concentration. Within the uncertainties, it is difficult to conclusively confirm or reject absorption enhancement due to lensing. However, no absorption enhancement due to coating was observed, while other studies report enhancement factors up to 2 (Schnaiter et al., 2005) or weaker enhancement between 1.1 and 1.3 (calculated for 532 nm from PAX, Kalbermatter et al. 2022) was observed.

An additional observation from the mobility size distributions (Figure 3 in D5) is that the width of the distribution decreases with the initial coating step. This is often interpreted as a collapse of fractal aggregates upon coating. Alternatively, it may result from the filling of voids within the fractal structure by condensed material. Both processes lead to a more compact particle morphology.

Figure 4 compares the measured MAC values for series A1 and A2 with model calculations based on the core-shell and fractal representations. The fractal model with a porous shell shows substantially better qualitative agreement with the experimental data. The granular model was tested for a compacted core of ($D_f \approx 3$) in the center of the particle and compared to a precise Mie-core-shell model with the result, that the absorption and scattering cross sections for both particles representations differ by 6% and 1%, respectively (not shown in this study). From this we conclude that the granularity model is valid (compared to experimental uncertainties) and can serve as simulation for coating growth on a preexisting core of any shape. The differences to the core-shell model therefore is the geometry of the core-shell particle. The more compact and centrally located the absorbing material is, the stronger the light absorption enhancement due to lensing. For the shown fractal particle, the displacement and the elongated structure lead to a reduced light absorption enhancement.

For the coating there are now two possible pathways. The first one is the classical way well accepted in the community.

- i) A coating for condensing of SOA on the soot particle would lead to a surrounding shell and, what is well accepted, to a collapsing by surface tension forces of the fractal to a more compact structure. A thick coating would lead to a more spherical shell and the predicted light enhancement by lensing.
- ii) Coating is not happening by condensation, but aggregation between the soot core and nucleated SOA material. The particles can grow by particle (nucleated SOA particles) to cluster (fractal soot) aggregation into a more spherical shape by preferentially filling voids (seen as apparent collapsing in the mobility size spectrum by reshaping soot), or by cluster (aggregated SOA at higher SOA concentrations) to cluster aggregation forming non spherical aggregates.

The second pathway is more speculative but could explain why light absorption enhancement is not observed. A combination of both pathways is also plausible, with initial condensation and restructuring at low SOA concentrations, followed by SOA nucleation and cluster-cluster aggregation at higher concentrations.

7.2. Filter-based photometer calibration factors

The dependence of the C-factor on particle size is one of the most important sources of uncertainty in filter-based absorption photometers. Figure 5 shows the instrument-specific C-factors at 450 and 808 nm as a function of the volume median diameter.

A pronounced size dependence is observed for AE33, AE36s, AE22, and BC-1054, whereas no significant dependence is found for MA200 and MA350. These differences can be attributed to the filter material. MA200 and MA350 use PTFE filters, which behave more like surface filters resulting in a shallow particle penetration. In contrast, in fiber filter the particles penetrate deeper into the filter matrix. Deeper in the filter the multiple scattering is higher. This leads to an enhanced light absorption by absorbing particles (Moteki et al., 2010; Nakayama et al., 2010; Müller et al., 2014)

The observed increase in C-factor for smaller particles is consistent with increased penetration depth, which amplifies multiple scattering effects and thus the apparent absorption. Among the Aethalometers, AE33 and AE36s show excellent agreement due to their identical filter type, while the AE22 exhibits deviations that can likely be attributed to its different filter material. The BC-1054 shows the strongest size dependence and the highest C-values among the instruments tested. The results further confirm that filter material and structure are dominant factors controlling the magnitude of the C-factor. Operating parameters such as face velocity may additionally influence particle penetration depth, which itself strongly depends on particle size.

C- factors in the present study range from 7 to 5.5 for AE33. Values reported in Renzi et al. (2026) range from about 4.4 at 120 nm to 2.8 at 450 nm. For field measurements Renzi et al. (2026) got values of about 2.35, which is in close agreement with ACTRIS recommendations. (Note: ACTRIS recommends a harmonization factor $H^*=1.76$, which is related to C and C_m via $H^* = C/C_m$). In summary, the C-values determined in this study are higher than values from Literature or used in the ACTRIS network. These differences currently remain unexplained.

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